

D6.1. Project website

Reinventing High-performance pOwer converters for heavy-Duty electric trAnSport

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

DOCUMENT CONTROL PAGE	2
REVISION HISTORY	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	2
DISCLAIMER	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
1.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DOCUMENT AND PURSUE	5
1.2 WPS AND TASKS RELATED WITH THE DELIVERABLE	5
2.1 TECHNICAL ASPECTS	6
2.2 HOSTING AND MAINTENANCE	6
2.3 ANALYTICS	6
2.4 PERSONAL DATA	6
2.5 WEBSITE STRUCTURE	6
2.6 HOME PAGE	7
2.7 WEBSITE SECTIONS	7
2.8 FUTURE MODIFICATIONS	10
2. CONCLUSION	11

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document briefly presents the structure of the RHODaS project website. RHODaS D6.1 is in fact the website itself, described in this document.

The aim of the website is to be the centre of attention for project's communication and dissemination activities.

The website is hosted in Spain and it has been developed with Drupal 9, an open source web content management system. Analytics tool have been implemented to monitor the access to the website.

The website (<https://www.rhodas.eu/>) is structured with the home page with different sections briefly presenting the project. The content of the website is structured into four different categories: "Project", "Dissemination", "News", "Events".

A content plan for publishing news has been put into place. The website will be maintained and updated with all needed sections and contents according to the needs of the project.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DOCUMENT AND PURSUE

This document describes the tools that have been put into place to build the RHODaS project website. The aim of the website is provide public project information to allow dissemination of non-confidential results.

1.2 WPS AND TASKS RELATED WITH THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable refers to Task 6.1 “Communication activities” and Task 6.1.2. “Project website” and included in WP6: Exploitation, communication and dissemination.

2.1 TECHNICAL ASPECTS

The website has been developed using Drupal v9. Drupal is an open-source content management framework written in PHP and distributed under the GNU General Public License. Compared to other content management systems, Drupal was selected for its versatility and robustness.

2.2 HOSTING AND MAINTENANCE

The website has been developed and will be maintained by KNEIA. The domain <https://www.rhodas.eu/> is hosted by RNet in Spain. KNEIA is responsible for the update of the information on the website throughout the duration of the project and for some time after the end of it.

2.3 ANALYTICS

The interactions with the webpage will be monitored with Google Analytics. In this way, it will be possible to track and report website traffic, if the visitor has agreed to do so allowing the tracking with cookies. Relevant indicators will be included in D6.3 “PDEC - Plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities” and in periodical technical report.

2.4 PERSONAL DATA

Visitors entering the website can contact the project with their names and personal e-mail. It is not foreseen to collect sensitive data, which, according to the GDPR, is personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data or biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health, sex life or sexual orientation.

When collecting the data, a checkbox where the user has to confirm the acceptance of the privacy policy with a direct link to the privacy policy is included.

2.5 WEBSITE STRUCTURE

The website can be accessed at <https://www.rhodas.eu/>. All the pages include a header and a footer with the project email, project social media, the project logo and the menu to navigate the website.

Figure 1: Header

The footer includes the official funding acknowledgement and the disclaimer according to the Grant Agreement indications, the link to the Privacy Policy page, to the contact form and the links to the LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube accounts of RHODaS.

Figure 2: Footer

2.6 HOME PAGE

The home page of the website is divided into different sections presenting summarised information on the project. There is also information on the latest news about the project and events, call to action to visit other pages of the website and to get in touch with the project. A slider of the partners of the consortium is also included.

Figure 3: Three of sections of the home page

2.7 WEBSITE SECTIONS

The website is divided into different sections, shown in the menu of the website as following:

- Project
 - About RHODaS: the main non-confidential information on the project is shown.

RHODaS Project

A NEW APPROACH TO POWER CONVERTERS

Challenges posed by the road transport

Classical road transport using fossil fuels in internal combustion engines (ICE) is one of the largest polluters, currently generating about 60 % of the total emissions released into the atmosphere from human activity.

Although passenger cars are the major source of pollution, light-duty and heavy-duty vehicles are not far behind, accounting for almost the 40% of total CO2 emissions from road transport in Europe. Thus, the electrification of these vehicles, especially heavy-duty types, is a promising strategy to limit environmental pollution, contributing significantly to the mitigation of global change, with its consequent societal benefits.

For the first time in 2020, EU truck manufacturers within the European Automobile Manufacturers' Association (ACEA) have expressed their commitment to decarbonise this sector by 2050 at the latest and trends show the rising interest and offer of heavy duty electric vehicles.

Truck manufacturers are investing heavily in new solutions, such as alternative fuels, batteries and hydrogen. Battery electric vehicles are the first zero-emission technology to reach the truck market and will be immediately followed by hydrogen-powered trucks. However, there is no standard solutions of powertrain components for the different models and types of vehicles available.

The RHODaS project is working on solutions to increase the stake of heavy-duty electric vehicles in road transport.

RHODaS Objectives

Objectives of the RHODaS project for greener mobility

The RHODaS project aims at developing disruptive topologies of power converters using new semiconductor materials as well as cutting-edge digital technologies to improve architecture efficiency, power density, reliability, cost and sustainability. Moreover, multi-disciplinary approaches of modular power electronics for Integrated Motor Drive (IMD) and ecodesign considerations are addressed, to create compact solutions that can be integrated in a wide range and heavy-duty, enabling these electric vehicles to be more sustainable and autonomous throughout the entire lifecycle of their components.

A more common, modular approach may unify design, manufacture, performance and safety requirements, to create a cost-efficient value chain in the EU, based on economies of scale, as a competitive advantage against Asian and USA manufacturers. Moreover, this approach will not only benefit EV car manufacturers but also complementary markets like urban mobility, transport and logistics, through the establishment of a Pan-European supply chain within the automotive sector that is based on effective circular economy models as the power electronics solutions can also be applied to light-duty vehicle types M and L.

Figure 4: About RHODaS page

- Impact: the Key Impact Pathways to be achieved by the project are listed and a brief explanation is reported.

Impact

RHODAS PATHWAYS TOWARDS IMPACT

In line with the European Green Deal objectives, the targets set in the Paris Agreement, the EU 2030 Climate & Energy Framework and the European Roadmap on the "Electrification of Road Transport", the research and innovation activities of the RHODAS project are expected to make measurable contributions in medium-term to achieve the targets displayed below.

Click on the icon on the left of each section to read the details of the RHODAS contribution to each Key Impact Pathway.

+	Demonstrate a minimum of 20% cost reduction of power electronic modules and inverters for a given power, to increase the overall affordability of EVs in mass production (in comparison to the cost of the best current-generation or close to market components at proposal submission time).
+	Significant advancements in efficiency (reduction of losses by 25%) and thermal performance (increased maximum operational temperature), both parameters versus the state of the art of the targeted application. This allows further driving range extension, faster charging and easier thermal management of the whole powertrain, as well as possible improvement in cabin-heating and defrosting in winter.
+	Development of power electronics enabling drastic size and weight reductions for the electric drive, with significant advances beyond 5 kW/kg or 20kW/litre for a BEV.
+	Facilitating the integration of power electronics in batteries/fuel cells and electric motors/axles (including modular approaches).
+	Increased reliability and availability of powertrain by intelligent control and diagnostics techniques, predictive maintenance of machine and inverter.
+	Achieve automotive quality levels in the whole system with new, robust and reliable functionalities and materials.
+	Towards climate-neutral and environmentally friendly mobility through clean solutions across all transport modes while increasing global competitiveness of the EU transport sector.
+	Accelerated uptake of zero tailpipe emission, affordable, user-centric solutions (technologies and services) for road-based mobility all across Europe.

Figure 5: Impact

- Partners: the partners list and their main tasks in the RHODAS project are presented.
- Industrial Advisory Board: a brief explanation on the role of the Industrial Advisory Board is presented. This page will be updated according to the activities carried out with the industrial advisory board.
- Related projects: a list of the projects related with the activities of RHODAS is shown.

RHODAS Related Projects

FUNDED PROJECTS WORKING ON SOLUTIONS FOR ZERO-EMISSION TRANSPORT

The project coordination will establish close collaboration with consortia developing related topics within the call "Clean and competitive solutions for all transport modes, Zero emission road transport (ZZERO), HORIZON-CLS-2021-05-01", as well as other EU and national funded projects. The details of the projects are available below.

SCAPE - Switching-Cell-Array-based Power Electronics conversion for future electric vehicles	PowerDrive - Power electronics optimisation for next generation electric vehicle components
<p>Start date: 01/07/2022 End date: 30/06/2026</p> <p>SCAPE aims at achieving three main objectives: i) propose a standardisable, modular, and scalable approach, based on multilevel technology, for the design of the EV power conversion systems ii) develop highly-compact and integrated building-block implementation, iii) propose intelligent modulation and control strategies, online diagnosis, and digital twin for predictive maintenance with machine learning. Reaching these objectives will enable reducing the cost of the EV power electronics thanks to scale economies, improving its performance features (reliability, efficiency, power density, etc.), and enabling advanced functionalities. This will allow satisfying the user's needs, increase the acceptance and affordability of zero-emission vehicles, reduce greenhouse gases emission, and enable a full-market penetration of the EV. Having this approach adopted by EU automotive manufacturers will allow creating a cost-efficient production chain in the EU based on economies of scale and advanced integration technologies, as a competitive advantage against other manufacturers.</p> <p>ID: 101056781</p> <p>Programme: HORIZON-CLS-2021-05-01 - Clean and competitive solutions for all transport modes, Zero emission road transport (ZZERO)</p>	<p>Start date: 01/05/2022 End date: 31/10/2025</p> <p>With the purpose of transforming road transportation in Europe to zero-emission mobility, POWERDRIVE aims at developing next generation, highly efficient, cost-effective, and compact power electronics solutions that integrate a portfolio of technologies for multi-objective optimisation of electric powertrains of battery electric vehicles. These integrated solutions can be applied to both low and high-performance vehicles, and they will be suitable for diverse types of electric vehicles. The concept of POWERDRIVE is that all the experience and expertise of the project partners in the development of electric drivetrain components will be leveraged and lead into the integration of advanced power electronics solutions for an optimised powertrain. This concept brings additional opportunities to strengthen Europe's supply chain in electromobility for road transportation and to achieve zero-emission road mobility.</p> <p>ID: 101056857</p> <p>Programme: HORIZON-CLS-2021-05-01 - Clean and competitive solutions for all transport modes, Zero emission road transport (ZZERO)</p> <p>Project coordinator: KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN - BELGIUM</p>

Figure 6: Related projects

- Dissemination
 - Downloads: when available, leaflets, poster and other communication and dissemination materials will be available for the download.
 - Public deliverables: a list of all the public deliverables of the projects is present. After their acceptance by the European Commission, they will be uploaded to the website.

RHODaS Deliverables

PUBLIC DELIVERABLES FROM THE RHODAS PROJECT

On specific dates, periodic assessment reports called "deliverables" have to be submitted to the European Commission in order to evaluate the progress of the project. On this page, you can find the public documents from the RHODaS project.

Deliverable Number: D7.5

Gender Action Plan and Ethics considerations

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on the gender aspects of the project and provide a framework for addressing the various ethical issues related to the development, design, implementation and testing of the prototypes developed in the project. This deliverable will therefore describe the need and importance of promoting gender balance and equality transversely and how the ethics considerations are fulfilled throughout the project planning and implementation to stand out as an excellent example of a well-balanced working community.

Due date: 31/10/2022

ID: UPC

Deliverable Number: D6.3

PDEC - Plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities

This Deliverable describes the plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities within RHODaS. The objective of the PDEC is to identify and organise actions to promote the commercial exploitation of the project's results and achieve a wide dissemination of knowledge from the project. It will consider the communication needs, objectives and goals, target audiences, key message, sources, communication channels, barriers, action plans and results evaluation. In addition, a dissemination tool kit with templates and materials for dissemination and communication is provided. This deliverable will be updated in M24 and in M42.

Due date: 31/10/2022

Figure 7: Public deliverables

- News: all the news on the project will be published in this page.
- Events: events where RHODaS partners will participate and events related with RHODaS activities will be shown.
- Contact: a contact form where the visitors can get in touch with the project management is available.
- Search: a tool to look for specific information in the project page.

2.8 FUTURE MODIFICATIONS

As the project evolves, the website will be adapted accordingly. A content plan to publish news on the project has been put into place and events will be updated periodically. A "Publications" page, already designed, will be uploaded as soon as the first open access articles are available.

2. CONCLUSION

This deliverable has presented the structure of the RHODaS project website. The different sections can be modified and updated according to the communication and dissemination needs that may arise during project implementation.

The website will be maintained by KNEIA at least 5 years after the project's end.